

INFLUENCE OF RECLAMATION TYPE OF SUBSIDENCE RESERVOIRS ON VEGETATION DIFFERENTIATION IN SURROUNDING AREA

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Abstract

The paper presents the impact of reclamation of subsidence reservoirs on diversity of vegetation of areas in the vicinity of Karviná (Czech Republic). This work included results of the studies carried out in areas subjected to various types of reclamation (natural, mixed and artificial). Floristic analysis of phytocoenoses forming spontaneously through succession succeeded by the most frequently used technical-biological reclamation method was conducted. The vegetation diversity indicate similar course of processes of vegetation formation both under natural conditions and by reclamation activities when it is succeeded by natural processes. In the site where technical-biological reclamation was performed, species composition and their contribution are markedly distinct. There, high contribution of ubiquitous species is observed. The results reveal that reclamation method has considerable impact on type of vegetation growing in the vicinity of subsidence reservoirs.

Keywords: *post mine subsidence reservoirs, reclamation, vegetation*

Introduction

The regions, where due to mineral resources abundance exploitation industry is being developed in last 100 years, is characterized by profound natural environment transformations (Rostański 2006). One of such deformations are so-called subsidence reservoirs forming by collapse of earth over exploitation field.

Such subsidences sites very frequently become flooded, what results in forming of anthropogenic water bodies (Maciak 2003), increasing mosaic of environment and enhancing biodiversity in their neighbourhood (Szczepanek 2003; Sierka and Sierka 2008).

However, as some studies demonstrate the manners of restoration of use values of the areas transformed by mining activity (type of reclamation) are essential from the viewpoint of origin of different biotopic conditions, directly affecting vegetation formation (Stalmachová 1996).

Thus, currently three types of reclamation may be distinguished:

- natural one - consisting on using vegetation forming in the process of spontaneous succession;
- mixed one - based on "collaboration with nature" so called, method of directed succession;
- artificial one - omitting benefits from restoration of nature, based on technical and biological treatments,

Studies were started which aimed at estimation of effects of various types of reclamation management expressed by vegetation diversity in area surrounding subsidence reservoirs.

Study area

Two subsidences reservoirs occurring within Karviná commune became the objects of the study (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Localization of study objects.
Explanation: 1- subsidences reservoirs.

First reservoir (I) located in northern part of Karvina – Louki was subjected to reclamation using spontaneous succession method, which led to formation of habitats and refuges for rare and protected plants and creation of biological, esthetical and scientific function (Stalmachová 1992).

The second reservoir “Darkowskie Morze” (II) was subjected to technical and biological reclamation. In small fragments of banks reclamation by directed succession method was performed. In these sites special type of a habitat was prepared for development of rush vegetation (Stalmachová 1992).

Materials and methods

Data were gathered on study plots laid out within areas in the vicinity of the two water bodies formed due to flooding of subsidence basins by stream Mlinka.

Tab. 1. Characteristics of study plots.

	Study plot A	Study plot B	Study plot C
Reservoir	Nerodek	Darkow	Darkow
Slope of bank	-	2°	10°
Reclamation method	Spontaneous succession	Directed succession	Technical-biological reclamation
Treatments	Lack	Modification of biotopic conditions	Filling with barren rock, planting of <i>Cornus mas</i>

In total, studies were carried out in 3 sample plots together covering of ca 70 m². The study plots were transects 11 m long and 2 m wide. The basic subplots were of 1m².

In particular basic subplots vertical structure of phytocoenoses and species composition in specific layers were estimated. Percentage cover of species in squares with a side of 1 m were evaluated using the following scale 0%, 1%, 5%, 10%, 20%.....100%. Plant species, with their percentage were classified into syngenetic groups.

The plant nomenclature was adopted after Mirek et al. (2002). Syntaxonomical affinity of particular species followed Matuszkiewicz (2008).

Next, particular study plots, located within areas subjected to reclamation by method: spontaneous succession (A); reclamation with using directed succession (C) were compared due to floristic composition and percentage of syngenetic groups.

Results

The most diversified is phytocoenoses (A), caused through spontaneous succession, in relation to contribution of particular syngenetic groups. The highest contribution is made by species of the classes *Phragmitetea* (23%) and *Salicetea purpureae* (19%). Species of the *Alnetea glutinosae* class (6%) show the highest contribution in comparison with other study plots subjected to other types of reclamation.

The dominant group of species on the study plot, where processes of restoration are helped, rush species dominate, whereas species of the classes *Bidentetea tripartiti* (16%) and *Artemisietea vulgaris* (13%) make significant contribution.

On study plot C there the most abundant are species representing the classes *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* (48%), *Artemisietea vulgaris* (17%), *Stellarietea mediae* (7%) and species of lack of syntaxonomical affiliation – ubiquitous species (16%) (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Percentage participation of syngenetic groups in the study plots. (In figure classes with mean percentage lower than 2% were not shown)

The ordination of syngenetic groups of species with regard to study plots representing specific type of reclamation showed relationship between contribution of species of the *Phragmitetea* class and reclamation of study plot by directed succession and to lower degree with study plot underwent spontaneous succession of vegetation. For both types of reclamation species of the classes: *Salicetea purpurea* and *Epilobietea angustifolii* are associated. In study plot, where reclamation by biological-technical method was done domination of species representing classes *Artemisieteae vulgaris* and *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* was observed (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Results of Principal Component Analysis (PCA) – syngenetic groups of species and their contribution to particular manners of reclamation of subsidence reservoirs.

The importance of spontaneous succession as a effective method of reclamation of subsidence reservoirs is highlighted in works by Tokarska-Guzik and Rostański (1996, 2001) as well as by Stalmachová (1998, 2003). The results of studies on diversity of phytocoenoses adjacent to anthropogenic reservoir, abandoned for spontaneous succession indicated high contribution of characteristic and distinguishing species for classes forming in the vicinity of natural water bodies (*Phragmitetea*, *Salicetea purpurea* and *Alnetea glutinosae*). The vegetation caused in the process of spontaneous succession show higher species diversity and vertical structure and it is similar to forest communities which are more stable when compared to meadow and ruderal vegetation formed by man in processes of technical-biological reclamation and directed succession.

The possibility of acceleration and direction of succession processes by creation of proper habitat conditions is mentioned by Krzaklewski (1999). The examples of creation of forest and swamp vegetation on British Isles are given by Tokarska-Guzik and Rostański (2001).

Analysis of vegetation of phytocoenosis caused as a result of treatments of the directed succession method demonstrated its similarity to natural systems in contribution of syngenetic groups. It is manifested by higher participation of species of the classes" *Phragmitetea*, *Potametea* and *Bidentetea tripartiti*. However, structure of phytocoenosis reflects its initial stage of development. Thus, further studies on the course of vegetation differentiation in next stages of development are needed. Only

better recognition of this question let objectively estimate effectiveness of this manner of reclamation, practical applicability in reclamation of post-industrialized areas and possibility of reduction of costs of that activity by using natur potential.

It seems that only modification of biotopic conditions for spontaneous development of vegetation is insufficient. It would be necessary to plant shrub species of the *Salicetea purpureae* in more humid sites and species of the *Rhamno-Prunetea* class – in drier sites both in distant vicinity of the reservoir. It would accelerate the process of differentiation of vertical structure of community and reduce the expansion of such species as *Calamagrostis epigejos*. Probably it might influence on the increase of biodiversity and stability of ecosystem. Similar suggestions are given by Stalmachová (2003).

The phytocoenosis caused by technical-biological reclamation method, is the most deviant from natural communities in relation to participation of syngenetic groups. Low participation of species of the *Phragmitetea* class and considerable contributions of classes *Artemisietea vulgaris*, *Stellarietea mediae* show ruderal character of man-made phytocoenoses. The domination of species of the *Molinio-Arrhenatheretea* class and the presence of the *Festuco-Brometea* class indicate different type of habitat. Yet Makohuzová (2001) and Stalmachová (2003) reported that ruderalization of areas subjected to that type of reclamation and as a results of that creation of habitat conditions preclude spontaneous development of rush and swamp vegetation.

Drawing such conclusions about efficiency of particular methods of reclamation is well-founded only for studied objects, which are different in many aspects and it should treat them individually (Sierka et al., 2008).

This problem requires further complex research for purpose of improvement and contribution to knowledge on reclamation of environmental precious areas encompassing not only vegetation and biotopic conditions but whole ecosystem.

Conclusions

1. In the light of obtained data, subsidence reservoirs in post-industrial areas should be maintained and subjected to reclamation by natural succession, whereas using technical-biological reclamation should be reduced for purpose of protection of valuable communities and their biotopes.
2. Reclamation by directed succession method seems to be alternative for technical-biological reclamation, however, detailed instructions for their usage require precision aiming at achievement of higher efficiency of such type of reclamation.

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